

Determinants of Implementation of Special Groups' Procurement Contracts in Public Universities in Kenya

¹ Longo Kajuju Agnes, ²Dr. Samson Nyangau Paul

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8122370>

12Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology, Nairobi, Kenya

Abstract: The purpose of the study was to find out the determinants of the implementation of public procurement opportunities for special groups in the public universities in Kenya. The study was guided by the following objectives: information access, finance access, technical readinesses and finally compliance enforcement in relation to the implementation of public procurement opportunities for special groups in public universities in Kenya. A cross-sectional survey design was adopted by the study and both qualitative and quantitative methods was applied. The target population was all 39 public universities in Kenya. A sample of 68 procurement as well as finance officials from public universities was used. Questionnaire was used to collect the data. A pilot study was carried out to measure both reliability and validity of the research instruments. Tables and graphs was used to present the results. Regarding access to information, the study established that access to information had a significant and positive effect on the implementation of public procurement opportunities for special groups. The study established that access to finance had a significant and positive effect on the implementation of public procurement opportunities for special groups. The study also established that technical readiness had significant and a positive effect on the implementation of public procurement opportunities for special groups. The study finally established that compliance enforcement on had significant and a positive effect on the implementation of public procurement opportunities for special groups. The study recommends that public universities in the country should effectively integrate procurement functions with ICT based systems that can enhance implied tendering requirements through application of e-procurement methods; use of automated procurement systems as well as implementation of supportive ICT infrastructure for encouraging adoption of ICT based procurement systems. In addition, the study recommended that the public universities in the country should enhance efficient and effective procurement structures, policies and procedures as well imposing sanctions for violation of procurement rules that will boost implementation of public procurement opportunities for special groups.

Keywords: Access to Information, Access to Finance, Technical Readiness , Compliance Enforcement

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the study

Most of the global policy agendas and declarations continue to emphasis on the participation of special groups and enterprises owned by them in the public and private sectors. The United Nations (UN) Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) have obligated countries to adopt affirmative action (AA) strategies to ensure equal opportunities for special groups (Basheka & Auriacombe, 2020). It is all things considered saw that financial plans that avoid

extraordinary social gathering's premium are bothersome to the overall money related progress of nation states. The world over, challenges impacting use of public creation secure with openings have pulled in the thought from examiners, experts, academicians and experts in light of alarming demonstrating working out as expected considering non-adherence to certified cycles and frameworks.

Public obtainment has become an issue of public thought and chat, and has been the focus to changes, modifying, rules and regulations. Most countries both in made and least made countries have set up procurement changes including laws and rules. The huge hindrance in any case, has been insufficient utilization of public not securing to unprecedented social occasions. de Boer and Telgen(1998) confirm that usage of public acquisition to extraordinary groups affect just the underdeveloped nations yet in addition nations in the created world. This position is additionally upheld by Gelderman, Paul and Brugman(2006) who fight that usage of public procurement to unprecedented social events in open acquisition is so far a critical issue. Public acquisition is a fundamental restriction of governments in both made and non-current nations as the monstrous monetary outpourings immensely impacts their economies that needs insightful association. As such sensible treatment of public making sure about cutoff points is head to accomplishing financial, socio-political and different protests of government (Thai and Grimm, 2000).

1.2 Statement of the problem

Public procurement takes up to 10–15% of gross domestic product (GDP) in developed countries and over 30% of GDP in developing countries. This adds up to trillions of dollars of government spending annually (International Trade Centre (ITC), 2014). Transparency international (2013) notes that, in Kenya special groups makes up to over 85% of the entire population yet they contribute to less than 10% of public procurement involvement thus this hampers economic growth and achievement of vision 2030. Special groups have indicated that amongst the challenges that hinder them in accessing public procurement opportunities include; lack of access to credit, capacity building, inadequate skills, poor information and inhibitive legal regulatory framework (Kariuki & Mwangi, 2013; Nduta et al., 2015; Nkonge, 2013).

Public procurement practitioners have always faced many challenges in many countries both developed and developing. According to Wangai (2012), the bidding process in the Kenyan public procurement is not fair and transparent which poses a great challenge to the special groups ability to participate in public procurement activities. Although the Kenya government has put in place legal frameworks for competitive and transparent public procurement, implementation of these frameworks has not been done fully in public sector to due to inadequate access to information, inadequate access to finances, minimal technical readiness and improper compliance enforcement (Muraguri, 2013; Mwangi, 2017; Wanjiru & Wanyoike, 2018).

Studies on the area that have focused their research on the effect of procurement systems in companies include; Ogembo-Kachieng'a and Ogara(2004) found out that procurement and management of health equipment required changes in the approach as it determined the quality of the healthcare services in the hospitals. Achuora, Arasa and Ochiri(2005) examined the effectiveness of public procurement audits for constituency development funds in Kenya. However, they did not review the factors that influence special groups 'access to procurement opportunities on Kenyan public universities. Karanja and Mugo (2010) and Wleh(2015) examined the impact of procurement activities on the operation and effectiveness of public sectors in Kenya with focus of youths and concluded that it is essential that procurement activities are performed by qualified staff with high professional and ethical standards. However, they did not examine the factors influencing special groups 'access in the context of Kenyan public universities.

Muraguri(2013) notes that the implementation of the special groups preference and reservations policy in public

procurement on state owned enterprises in Nairobi had not been fully implemented. Gatere and Shale (2014) in their study on the challenges affecting the implementation of access to government procurement opportunities for special interest groups in Kenya concluded that the legal framework has a duty to facilitate the implementation of access to government procurement opportunities for Special Interest groups in Kenya. All the studies reviewed lacked conclusive review of the factors influencing the implementation of public procurement opportunities for special groups in the context of Kenyan public universities. Majority of the studies focus on reservations and preference policies in county governments and state corporations with focus on special groups. This forms the research gap that this study seeks to fill. Thus, this study sought to answer the following question; determinants of implementation of special groups' procurement contracts in public universities in Kenya.

1.3 Objectives of the study

- (i) To determine the influence of access to information on the implementation of special groups' procurement opportunities in public universities in Kenya.
- (ii) To found out the influence of access to finance on the implementation of special groups' procurement opportunities in public universities in Kenya.
- (iii) To investigate the influence of technical readiness on the implementation of special groups' procurement opportunities in public universities in Kenya.
- (iv) To investigate the influence of compliance enforcement on the implementation of special groups' procurement opportunities in public universities in Kenya.

2. THEORITICAL FRAMEWORK

2.0 Theory

2.1 Preferential Procurement Model

Procurement can be used to support socio-economic policies using a number of approaches that includes reservation, referencing, indirect strategies and supply side measures. A preferential procurement policy refers to that policy that advocate for the objectivity in the procurement as noted by (Simayi, 2005).Acquirement with respect to arrangements have been all around used to accomplish different monetary and political mission.As indicated by Mwangi (2017),reservation, preferencing, backhanded procedures and deftly side measures are huge standard plans related to ensuring about that are used to achieve monetary goalsSpecification organizes that all securing contracts are done in agree to the current philosophies that are identified with obtaining(Arrowsmith, Treumer, Fejø, and Jiang, 2011).cash related objectives through getting(Simayi, 2005).Notwithstanding, hazards related with a program of acquirement can be restricted should the execution imagining that has the most un-negative impact be gotten and this framework be done inside an overall portrayed structure.

2.2 Mc Mullen – Shepherd Model

The Mc Mullen – Shepherd Model was articulated byMcMullen and Shepherd(2006) trying to excuse pioneering conduct concerning existing chances. As shown by the speculation, business visionaries follow up on what they perceive is an opportunity. Since conditions exist in (or make or perhaps make) high inadequacy, business visionaries must use their judgment about whether to act. Thusly, to comprehend starting improvement one must

have the choice rather than graph the degree of deficiency saw to envelop a commonplace possibility and the individual's status to suffer through that inadequacy. The individual's prior data can decrease the degree of deficiency, and their motivation shows capacity to bear vulnerability(Hisrich, 2005). McMullen-Shepherd model shows how information and inspiration in this way two times of leading activity.

2.3 Critique of Existing Literature

Implementation of public procurement policies in public institutions today is tailored around enough funding and effective use of the available financial resources Njoroge and Ngugi, (2016). The implementation framework must be within the applicable Laws and regulations. The legal regime does not put into consideration the special circumstances of the disadvantage groups, which must also adhere to the procurement Laws and regulations. The study by Wanjiru and Wanyoike, (2018) revealed that the tender evaluation process was the most important

determinant affecting the participation of special groups-owned companies' in public procurement tenders. The tendering process is a resource intensive and requires skills to prepare the tender as per the terms of reference set out in the tender documents (Wanjiru et al., 2018). The study recommends the arrangement consortiums whenever offering in order to build their odds of being granted tenders. In any case, the uncommon gatherings do not have the monetary ability to connect with legitimate administrations that will unite them to frame a consortium that will be serious.

The studies by Odero and Ayub, (2017) and Korir and Wanambiro, (2017) put accentuation on association arranging, staff skills and financing plan for unique gatherings. Luckily, there are a large group of monetary instruments being offered by different foundations, including neighborhood buy request (LPO) financing and receipt limiting. There is likewise the Uwezo Fund and the young and undertaking reserve. A significant obstruction is the installment cycle since handling a receipt takes months bringing about deferred installments and defaulting on credit commitments.

2.4 Research Gaps

A vast number of scholars have researched on the factors affecting participation of special groups in government business opportunities as highlighted in this review. Most studies focused on the factors influencing the uptake of government tenders from specific point of view of the either youth, women and people with disabilities which largely revolved around financing, registration, and capacity to deliver (Mwangi, 2017; Wleh, 2015). Other studies focused on ethical issues, planning and legal challenges of mainly youths. This study is unique in that it will look at the factors from the point of view of the procurement and finance practitioners from public universities that is tasked with the implementation of the affirmative action initiatives from combined special groups.

2.5 Summary

A vast number of scholars have researched on the factors affecting participation of special groups in government business opportunities as highlighted in this review. Most studies focused on the factors influencing the uptake of government tenders from the point of view of the special groups which largely revolved around financing, registration, and capacity to deliver. Other studies focused on ethical issues, planning and legal challenges. This study is unique in that it will look at the factors from the point of view of the procurement and finance practitioners from government ministries that is tasked with the implementation of the affirmative action initiatives.

3 METHODOLOGY

The researcher used descriptive research design. The target population of this study therefore was all 39 public universities in Kenya. The current study comprised of 39 Public universities, which is relatively small size population and hence no need of sampling. Out of 39 Public universities, 5 Public universities were used in the pilot study thus remaining with 34 Public universities., a census will be carried out for this study. 2 respondents were selected from each public university bringing a total of 68 respondents. This study used primary data which was collected through use of questionnaires. A five-point Likert scale questionnaire was used. The researcher contracted two research assistants to collect data. The collected data from the questionnaire was been given codes, keyed in the computer and eventually edited for completeness. Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) and Microsoft Excel was used data analysis.

Model

Analysis of data used multiple regressions to test the research questions

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \epsilon$$

Where;

Y= Implementation of special groups procurement opportunities.

β_0 =constant

β_i is the coefficient for X_i ($i=1, 2, 3, 4$)

X_1 = Information access

X_2 = Finance access

X_3 = Technical readiness

X_4 = Compliance enforcement

$\beta_1 \beta_2 \beta_3 \beta_4$ = Regression co-efficients

ϵ = error term

4. REGRESSION RESULTS

Table 1: Model summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.970 ^a	.941	.937	.33379
a. Predictors: (Constant), Access to information, Access to finance, technical readiness, Compliance enforcement				

A multiple linear regression analysis was performed to test the effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The average ratings for the four independent variables. The coefficient of determination and standard error of the regression model are shown in Table 4.13 above. Results indicate that R squared was 0.941 indicating that the independent variables explained 94.1% of the implementation of public procurement opportunities for special groups in public universities in Kenya. This indicates the model had good explanatory power. Further, the regression output in Table 4.14 presents the source of variance, mean of variances and the F value. The results indicate that the overall model was significant (f value = 230.691; $p < 0.05$) and could provide important results. This indicates that the model could provide some predictive significance and was a good fit

Table 3: Analysis of Variance of the Regression (ANOVA)

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	102.808	4	25.702	230.691	.000 ^b
	Residual	6.462	59	.111		
	Total	109.270	63			
a. Dependent Variable: Implementation of Public procurement opportunities						
b. Predictors: (Constant): Access to information, Access to finance, technical readiness, Compliance enforcement						

Further, the regression output on significance of the independent variables is presented in Table 2.

Table 3: Significance of Independent Variables

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.308	.114		2.707	.000
	Access to information	.885	.052	.909	17.087	.000
	Access to finance	.911	.040	.946	22.802	.002
	technical readiness	.926	.034	.962	27.409	.003
	Compliance enforcement	.923	.043	.939	21.269	.004

a. Dependent Variable: implementation of Public procurement opportunities

The optimal regression model was:

$$Y=0.308+0.885X_1+0.911X_2+0.926X_3+0.923X_4+\epsilon$$

The regression equation above has established that taking all factors into account (information access, finance access, technical readiness and compliance enforcement) constant at zero, implementation of Public procurement opportunities will be 0.308. The findings presented also show that taking all other independent variables at zero, a unit increase in the information access would lead to a 0.885 increase in the scores of implementation of public procurement opportunities and a unit increase in the scores of finance access would lead to a 0.911 increase of implementation of public procurement opportunities. Furthermore, unit increase in the technical readiness would lead to a 0.926 increase in the scores of implementation of public procurement opportunities. Finally, the findings shows that a unit increases in the scores of compliance enforcement would lead to a 0.923 increase in implementation of public procurement opportunities

5.CONCLUSION

Regarding access to information, the study established that access to information had a significant and positive effect on the implementation of public procurement opportunities for special groups in public universities in Kenya. The study also established that access to finance had a significant and positive effect on the implementation of public procurement opportunities for special groups in public universities in Kenya. The study further established that technical readiness had significant and a positive effect on the implementation of public procurement opportunities for special groups in public universities in Kenya. The study finally established that compliance enforcement on had significant and a positive effect on the implementation of public procurement opportunities for special groups in public universities in Kenya.

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